

Farm machinery

Effect of soil moisture content on power requirements

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We measured power requirements at different soil moisture levels, with soil moisture as the main factor and plowing depth as the subfactor in a split-plot design with four replications.

Soil was red yellow Podzolic with clayey texture. The area at Pulung Kencana Village, North Lampung District, Lampung Province, was flat and covered by cogon grass *Imperata cylindrica*. The cogon grass was cut and burned before the experiment started.

Treatments were 10, 15, 20, and 30% (wet basis) soil moisture and 10, 15, and 20 cm plowing depth. Plowing width was 20 cm and tractor speed was 5.4 km/h (1.5 m/s) using a 4-wheel 45-hp tractor IH354 and a 9-hp Kubota hand tractor.

Soil draft resistance was measured by fixing a drawbar dynamometer between the 4-wheel tractor and the hand tractor. Drawing power required was calculated as

$$P_{wr} = \frac{\text{resistance (kgf)} \times \text{speed (m/s)}}{75}$$

Table 1. Average soil draft resistance at 5 soil moisture levels and 3 plowing depths. North Lampung, Indonesia.

Plowing depth (cm)	Average soil draft resistance ^a (kgf)				
	10%	15%	20%	25%	30%
10	815.0 b	787.5 b	750.0 a	922.5 c	1175.0 h
15	920.0 c	907.5 c	825.0 b	1137.5 g	1290.0 j
20	1040.0 f	922.5 e	967.5 d	1225.0 i	1400.0 k
CV Soil moisture (%)	2.3				
Plowing depth (cm)	1.7				

^aMeans with the same letter do not differ significantly at 5% level by DMRT.

Table 2. Power requirements at various levels of soil moisture and plowing depth. North Lampung, Indonesia.

Soil moisture (%)	Plowing depth (cm)	Power requirement	
		hp	kW
10	10	16.3	12.2
	15	18.4	13.7
	20	20.8	15.5
15	10	15.8	11.7
	15	18.2	13.5
	20	19.9	14.8
20	10	15.0	11.2
	15	16.5	12.3
	20	19.4	14.5
25	10	18.5	13.8
	15	22.8	17.0
	20	24.5	18.3
30	10	23.5	17.5
	15	25.8	19.2
	20	28.0	20.0

Where, Pwr = required drawing power (hp),
resistance = total soil draft resistance, and
speed = speed of tractor.

Draft resistance differed significantly with soil moisture levels and plowing depths (Table 1). Highest resistance was at 30% soil moisture and 20 cm plowing depth.

For all plowing depths, draft resistance was higher at 25 and 30% soil moisture levels. At 10% soil moisture, the hard, cohesive soil was difficult to cut and invert. At 15 and 20% moisture levels, soil was easy to till and resistance was relatively low.

Plowing depth also contributed to high draft resistance: the deeper the cut, the higher the resistance, primarily because of the large volume of soil cut and inverted.

Soil draft resistance is linearly proportionate to power requirements: the higher the resistance, the more power needed to draw the plow at the same speed (Table 2).□

Postharvest technology

Uric acid content of stored rice

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Uric acid, the main constituent of insect excreta, is taken as an index of insect infestation. We studied IR8, PR108, and Basmati 370, representing coarse, medium, and fine varieties, harvested at three different times (7 d early, recommended maturity, 7 d late) with 3

replications. One lot was stored at original moisture content (IR8—23.1, 19.6, 19%; PR108—22.3, 18.8, 18%; Basmati 370—19.2, 17.5, 19%) and one lot was dried to 12% moisture with a forced air circulation dryer and stored. Both lots were stored in gunny bags under ambient conditions for 1, 6, and 12 mo.

Harvest time was not significantly correlated with uric acid content of milled rice (see table). Uric acid content significantly increased with duration of

Effect of harvest time, drying, and length of storage on uric acid content of milled rice. Ludhiana, India.

Variety	Harvest time	Uric acid content (mg/100 g)							
		Without drying				With drying			
		1 mo	6 mo	12 mo	Mean	1 mo	6 mo	12 mo	Mean
IR8	Early	4.13	8.64	10.50	7.76	3.75	9.00	9.00	7.25
	Normal	4.13	8.63	9.75	7.50	3.38	9.00	9.00	7.13
	Late	3.75	8.62	9.00	7.12	3.75	8.25	8.63	6.88
	Mean	4.00	8.63	9.75	7.46	3.63	8.75	8.88	7.09
PR108	Early	5.25	7.88	9.38	7.50	3.76	6.00	9.38	6.38
	Normal	4.50	7.50	9.00	7.00	3.75	6.38	7.50	5.88
	Late	4.50	6.75	10.13	7.13	3.74	6.75	7.50	6.00
	Mean	4.75	7.38	9.50	7.21	3.75	6.38	8.13	6.09
Basmati 370	Early	3.75	4.50	7.13	5.13	3.75	6.00	6.75	5.50
	Normal	4.88	6.75	7.13	6.25	3.75	6.00	7.13	5.63
	Late	4.50	6.00	6.38	5.63	3.38	5.63	6.00	5.00
	Mean	4.38	5.75	6.88	5.67	3.63	5.88	6.63	5.38

LSD (0.05) Harvest time = ns. Drying = 0.30.
Storage time = 0.36. Varieties = 0.36.

storage and was higher in samples stored without drying.

IR8 had higher uric acid content than PR108 and Basmati 370.

The predominant insect species found were *Corcyra cephalonica*, *Sitophilus oryzae*, and *Sitotroga cerealella*. □

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Farming systems

Establishing wheat with minimal tillage and irrigation after rice

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We grew rice - wheat - jute in a 2-yr field experiment 1983-85 in a low-lying field. IR579 rice (120 d duration) was grown in both wet seasons, direct seeded and transplanted, with 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha. UP-262 wheat (120 d duration) was grown with 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha immediately after rice (mid-Nov) with two levels of irrigation and four levels of tillage. Rupali jute (90 d duration for fiber) was sown in mid-Apr with 50-25-25 kg NPK/ha and fiber was measured the third wk of Jun for direct seeded rice and Jul for transplanted rice.

The experiment was laid out in a split-split-plot design, with rice in the main plot, irrigated wheat in the subplot, and wheat tillage after rice in the sub-subplot, with four replications. The soil of the experimental site (22.39° N, 88.54° E) was alluvial, with 0.55%

Effect of rice planting method, irrigation, and tillage in wheat after rice on yields of rice, wheat, and jute in West Bengal, India, 1983-85.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)			
	Rice ^a	Wheat	Jute	Total
<i>Rice planting method</i>				
Broadcast	1.8	2.8	0.7	5.3
Transplanted	2.4	2.2	0.8	5.4
LSD (0.05)	ns	ns	ns	
<i>Tillage^b for wheat after rice</i>				
No tillage	2.9	2.0	0.7	5.6
Minimum tillage	2.9	2.6	0.8	6.3
Normal tillage	3.0	2.8	0.7	6.5
Irrigation + normal tillage	2.9	2.4	0.7	6.1
LSD (0.05)	ns	ns	ns	
<i>Irrigation in wheat</i>				
At crown root initiation + flowering	3.1	2.4	0.8	6.3
At crown root initiation, late tillering, flowering, milk stage	2.8	2.5	0.7	6.0
LSD (0.05)	ns	ns	ns	-

^a Av of 2 yr. ^b No tillage = soil between rice rows opened with hand-drawn tine. Minimum tillage = 2 plowings with bullock, lengthwise and crosswise, followed by laddering. Normal tillage = 4 plowings with bullock, lengthwise and crosswise, followed by laddering.

organic C, 16 kg P/ha, 21 kg K/ha, and pH 6.9.

Broadcast and transplanted rice yields did not significantly differ (see table).

The cumulative effect of tillage and irrigation in wheat also did not significantly affect rice yield.

Wheat grain yields after rice, rice planting method, tillage operation, and irrigation did not differ significantly.

Jute fiber yield did not differ significantly with tillage and irrigation in preceding wheat.

In total production, transplanted rice was better than direct seeded. Four plowings and two plowings were equally good for wheat, but two irrigations were better than four irrigations. □

A rice-based intercropping sequence for Vindhyan red loam soils of eastern Uttar Pradesh

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Potential annual yield of crops on well-drained Vindhyan red soils (based on water availability and soil waterholding capacity) is estimated at 2-4 t/ha. But actual production is only 0.5-1 t/ha. The wet season is the main cropping season and upland rice occupies most of the area.